

Impact of initial sediment conditions on numerical modelling of bedload transport

Martin Utz

Dept. of Hydraulic Engineering

Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute (BAW)

Karlsruhe, Germany

martin.utz@baw.de

Abstract— The composition of river bed sediment is an important influencing factor of bedload transport. In numerical bedload transport models this composition is defined by the initial sediment condition, which specifies the grain size distribution at each calculation node. Probes, measurements taken from the field which yield sediment composition, are only available from limited locations within the calculation domain. From these point-based measurements assumptions must be made in regards to the spatial distribution of the sediment composition to define the initial sediment condition.

This study compares two different methods of generating a spatial distribution of the sediment composition, or in modelling terms the initial sediment condition. The first method uses pre-simulation and the second one uses spatial interpolation. The resulting differences of both methods are examined at two separate points during the modelling process: first at the generated initial conditions and second for the final results of the corresponding bedload transport simulations. The simulations are performed with TELEMAC-2D and SISYPHE.

The two methods lead to strong differences in the initial sediment conditions and also the bedload transport simulation results. Large differences are observed in bed level changes and bedload discharges. This study points out that a combination of both methods could be an appropriate way to generate an initial sediment condition.

I. INTRODUCTION

The composition of river bed sediment is an important influencing factor of the bedload transport. This composition is described by grain size distribution, which is variable in the horizontal direction as well as in the vertical. In numerical bedload transport models the river bed composition is defined by the initial sediment condition, which specifies the grain size distribution at each calculation node for each defined layer. The layers divide the subsurface of each cell vertically into domains of homogeneous properties and approximate the continuous vertical variability of the sediment composition [1]. The uppermost layer of the

river bed determines the amount of sediment which is available for transport and therefore significantly influences the amount of transported sediment. Furthermore, the underlying layers become important players in case of erosion. So it is critical that the initial sediment condition provides accurate information about the sediment composition in terms of the grain size distribution at each computation node and also in vertical direction. Measured grain size distribution of bed material is only available at limited probed locations, single spots, within the calculation domain. Therefore it is necessary to generate a spatial distribution of the sediment composition based on the measurements. The measurements include, for example, surface grab samples of the bed material, which are sieved afterwards to get the grain size distribution. The generated spatial distribution is then used as the initial sediment condition for a bedload transport simulation.

This study presents two different methods to generate a spatial distribution of the sediment composition and thus the initial sediment condition. The first method is based on a pre-simulation. One of the disadvantages of this approach is that it requires a huge effort in terms of computation time, because an additional simulation is needed to generate the initial sediment condition. Also it is unclear how well the natural composition of the river bed is described by the pre-simulation results. Therefore within this study another method is developed, which is significantly less costly than the pre-simulation. This second method uses a spatial interpolation of the measured grain size. In addition the interpolation ensures that the initial sediment condition resembles the measured data as close as possible.

Within this study, first, the differences in the initial sediment conditions itself are examined. Second, the influence of the different initial conditions on the results of a bedload transport simulation is investigated using a numerical bedload transport model of the Lower Rhine nearby Düsseldorf, which is a segment of the model used in [2].

II. GENERATION METHODS FOR THE INITIAL SEDIMENT CONDITION

A. Pre-simulation

The first approach uses a pre-simulation to generate the initial sediment condition. Within this approach the averaged grain size distribution of the measurements is used as initial sediment condition for the pre-simulation. This yields a spatial homogeneous distribution of the sediment composition at the beginning of the pre-simulation. We assume that the measurements are representative for the river bed material. Thus the homogeneous spatial distribution represents the average natural river bed material without typical spatial variability. Due to sediment transport during the pre-simulation, the grain size distribution at each calculation node changes yielding a non-homogeneous spatial distribution. The non-homogeneous spatial distribution aims to resemble nature and is then used as the initial sediment condition for the main simulation. In the pre-simulation, different hydraulic boundary conditions can be selected. A convenient choice is a natural hydrograph covering several years. Another possibility is to use a constant discharge which is decisive for the forming of the river bed. When using a natural hydrograph it is reasonable to use a time-averaged grain size distribution and not the grain size distribution occurring at the last time step of the pre-simulation. Otherwise the sediment composition could be too heavily influenced by the discharge situation at the end of the pre-simulation.

An advantage of the pre-simulation is that it works with a sparse data base, due to only the mean of the measured grain size distributions being used. However, by averaging the field measurements the local information is neglected. Therefore all of the available information is not being used completely. Another problem is that the pre-simulation should be conducted with the same numerical parameters as the calibrated model, because these describe the natural behaviour of the model best. Though, these parameters are not available during the generation of the initial sediment condition, as the model is not calibrated at that time. Therefore an iterative procedure is necessary, which significantly increases required effort. Another disadvantage is that during the simulation only the sediment composition in the topmost layers changes due to the sediment transport. In the underlying layers the constant distribution, which was set as the initial sediment condition of the pre-simulation, remains.

B. Spatial Interpolation

Spatial interpolation of measured grain size distribution is another approach for initial sediment condition generation. Usually measurement points are not close enough to perform an interpolation on a Cartesian coordinate system (Figure 1). Doing so would lead, especially in river bends, to unacceptable inaccuracies. Here the geometry of the river must be taken into account. A solution would be to perform the interpolation on a natural coordinate system somehow attached to the river. Unfortunately, the river geometry is not uniquely defined. In general a proper description of the river

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of the river axis, the hectometer profiles and the location of measurement points.

geometry must cover the longitudinal direction as well as the perpendicular one. The interpolation used for this study is based on the river axis to describe the longitudinal direction and the hectometre profiles for the perpendicular one (Figure 1). Both are common location elements in the field of waterway engineering. On this defined natural coordinate system a linear interpolation is performed between the measurement points. Model domain on the outer perpendicular edge of the outermost measurements is consistently extrapolated from the outermost points, yielding the grain size distribution directly from the closest relevant outermost point. A more detailed explanation of the interpolation method can be found in [3].

The spatial interpolation takes into account the measurements location and optimally transfers the information content of each measurement into the initial sediment condition. A drawback of spatial interpolation is its vulnerability to incorrect measurements and outliers. Therefore it is important to check the measured data carefully before performing any interpolation.

III. NUMERICAL MODEL AND INPUT DATA

A. Model Settings

The numerical investigations use a bedload transport model based on TELEMAC-2D and SISYPHE version v7p2r0. The model domain covers an 11 kilometres long stretch of the lower Rhine River (Rhine-km 738.5 – 749.5) near Düsseldorf, Germany (Figure 2). The model uses five layers to discretize the vertical structure of the subsurface. The simulated time period is 6.5 years, starting on 01.01.2000 and ending on 22.06.2006. The upstream hydraulic boundary condition is obtained using the gauge at Düsseldorf (Rhine-km 744.2) and the downstream boundary is defined by the relation between water level and discharge.

The sediment boundary condition is set as an equilibrium boundary condition. The model distinguishes two areas, erodible and non-erodible. The erodible area (Figure 2) covers the river bed, including the groyne fields. Only the erodible area is generated in the initial sediment condition. In the non-erodible area, sediment deposition is possible. This deposition can be eroded later, but no erosion additional beneath the initial bottom elevation can occur.

For this study the bedload transport model of Meyer-Peter and Müller is used with a MPM coefficient of 5 and a morphological factor of 4. In addition the Hiding and Exposure approach of Karim, Holly and Jang is applied with the secondary currents correction provided by SISYPHE. The layer model of Hirano-Ribberink is used for modelling the subsurface. The porosity is assumed to be constant within the simulation and is set to 18 percent. Within the hydrodynamic simulation the Multidimensional Upwind Residual Distribution N-Scheme is used for discretizing the advection term. The bottom friction is calculated with the friction law after Nikuradse. Further information about the chosen approaches can be found in the manuals of TELEMAC-2D [4] and SYSYPHE [5]. The settings proved to be reasonable in preceding studies.

Figure 2: Model domain with topography, erodible area, the gauge location and measurement points of the cutting samples.

B. Input Data Initial Sediment Condition

Overall there are three measurement campaigns available within the model domain, which have recorded the grain size distribution of the river bed material. The first was

conducted in 1983, the second in 1995 and most recently in 2011/2012. Unfortunately none of these campaigns matches the simulated time period. With 73 measurement points the campaign from 2011/2012 is the most extensive and therefore is used as the basis data for the initial sediment conditions. Figure 2 shows the location of the measurement points. At each location two surface grab samples are taken, to cover the vertical variation of the sediment composition. The sieving of the samples yields their corresponding grain size distributions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Initial Sediment Condition

Based on the methods explained in Section II two different initial sediment conditions are generated. These initial sediment conditions provide a grain size distribution at each calculation node, for each layer. The pre-simulation changes the grain size distribution only in the two topmost layers. Therefore in layers three to five a homogeneous mean grain size distribution is defined. In case of spatial interpolation for layers three to five the same interpolated distribution is used as in the second layer, as there is only measured data from the two topmost layers available.

In Figure 3 and Figure 4 the spatial distribution of the mean grain diameter is displayed for the two initial sediment conditions. The mean grain diameter is a basic characteristic describing the sediment composition. Figure 3 and Figure 4 are cropped images of the first river bend within the domain in order to better show discussed phenomena. Nevertheless all observations made within this bend are also valid for the rest of the model domain.

Figure 3: Initial sediment condition for the first layer, generated with a) the pre-simulation and b) the spatial interpolation

Figure 4: Initial sediment condition for the second layer, generated with a) the pre-simulation and b) the spatial interpolation

First consider Figure 3 which shows the initial sediment conditions for the first layer. Plot a) is generated by a pre-simulation and shows significant spatial variety. Only within the scour area is a constant mean grain size diameter noticeable. This shows one drawback of the pre-simulation. At the beginning of the pre-simulation this scour is covered by a layer of sediment with a thickness of a few decimetres. During the pre-simulation the covering is eroded, so that no information about the sediment composition in the scour area can be gained. Therefore the main grain size distribution in these areas is not only used as initial sediment condition for the pre-simulation, but also for the main simulation.

To prove if the spatial variety observed in plot a) corresponds with the measured data, we compare Figure 3 plot a) with plot b). This shows that the pre-simulation can't reproduce some basic phenomena, which are recognisable in the interpolated measured data, represented by plot b). For example the sorting of material within the bend, fine material in the inner side of the bend to the coarse material on the outer edge, is not properly reproduced by the pre-simulation. In addition the initial sediment condition generated by the pre-simulation shows a very strong coarsening at Rhine-km 741 in the outer edge. This coarsening is not visible in the interpolated data. During the pre-simulation a large amount of erosion takes place causing an overall coarsening of material at this location which cannot be backed by the measured data. So, one has to conclude, that the aim of the pre-simulation to resemble a

natural spatial distribution of the sediment composition is only reached to a limited degree. From this information one can conclude that the pre-simulation, where the goal is to generate a natural spatial distribution, has apparent limitations.

One major disadvantage to the second method, spatial interpolation, is the extrapolation of the most outer measurement points which leads, potentially, to unrealistic grain size distributions in the groyne fields. For example between Rhine-km 742 and 743 a larger mean grain size diameter leads to armouring, which is realistic in the main channel, but not within groyne fields. Thus, in absence of measurement points within groyne fields, the spatial interpolation leads to non-physical phenomena in the model, i.e. armouring in groyne fields. Additional measurement points in the relevant areas could solve this problem. An alternative is to make assumptions about the expected grain size distribution in the groyne fields and provide this information by fictitious measurement points to the interpolation.

Figure 4 shows the mean grain size diameters of the second layer. It is significant, that the mean grain size diameters of the interpolated initial sediment condition are much smaller than the mean grain size diameters of the initial sediment condition generated by the pre-simulation. This shows that the performed pre-simulation is not capable of properly reproducing the vertical distribution of the river bed material. The dark areas in Figure 4 represent the coarse material of the scours.

Table 1 emphasizes the primary problem of the pre-simulation method to reproduce the vertical structure of the river bed. Here the coarsening tendency is visible. This coarsening tendency is a general and well known problem, which can occur when using the bed layer model of Hirano-Ribberink and is not, in particular, a problem of the pre-simulation [1]. But it does point to the general problem. The pre-simulation amplifies issues and uncertainties from the numerical model by also embossing them to the initial sediment condition.

Table 1: Mean grain size diameter, averaged over the erodable area without the scours and the averaged grain size diameter of the measurements

Averaged mean grain size diameter	Initial sediment condition generated with		Measurements
	Pre-simulation	Spatial interpolation	
Layer 1	26.7 mm	22.8 mm	25.7 mm
Layer 2	25.0 mm	17.7 mm	21.1 mm

B. Numerical Bedload Transport Model

The numerical bedload transport model is calibrated for the initial sediment condition generated by the pre-simulation. There is no de novo recalibration performed for the simulation with the initial sediment condition generated by the spatial interpolation. Thus it is ensured that the differences in the simulation results are solely caused by the differences in the initial sediment condition.

The differences between the initial sediment conditions discussed in the last section lead to significant differences in the bed level changes. That holds true for local bed level changes (Figure 5) as well as for the erosion rate (Figure 6). Comparing plot a) and b) of Figure 5 it shows, that the areas with sediment deposition correspond well, whereas the erosions differ significantly. The results of the numerical bedload transport simulations are highly sensitive in regard to the initial sediment condition. It appears that the initial sediment condition with finer bed material, generated by the spatial interpolation, increases the erosions significantly. The comparison of measured erosion rates to the simulated erosion rates (Figure 6) shows that the initial sediment condition based on the pre-simulation yields a good accordance. The variant based on spatial interpolation shows clear deviation from the measured erosion rate during the first four years. A de novo calibration could reduce this deviation, but between 2004 and 2006 the simulated erosion rate corresponds well to the measured one. Therefore it seems probable that the erosion at the beginning of the simulation is at least partially caused by initial effects of the model. These initial effects fail to appear for the variant with

Figure 5: Erosion rates, calculated as bed level changes, averaged over the erodible area. The measured erosion rate is documented in [6]

pre-simulation, because they have already occurred during the pre-simulation.

The annual bedload discharges are not as sensitive to the initial sediment condition as the bed level changes (Figure 7). Both variants are able to reproduce the estimated annual bedload discharges in a proper way. It is noticeable, that the variant based on spatial interpolation, in this study, hits the estimation very well. The estimation is based on the relation of the discharge to the bedload discharge and the hydrographs for the considered period. The relation of the discharge to the bedload discharge is derived from the bed load transport measurements, which are taken regularly at Rhine-km 749.

V. CONCLUSION

This study compares two different methods to generate the initial sediment condition for numerical bedload transport simulations. The first one is based on a pre-simulation and the second one on a spatial interpolation. Both methods use sediment composition measurements to generate a data set, which provides information about the grain size distribution at each calculation node of the model domain and defines therefore the initial sediment condition.

It appears that the two approaches lead to significant differences in the initial sediment conditions. Taking the measurements as a best guess of the natural sediment composition we have, it becomes clear that the pre-simulation can only roughly resemble the natural composition of the river bed. Some basic phenomena such as the sorting of bed material over the cross section within river bends cannot be reproduced properly by the pre-simulation. The interpolation method yields good results in areas with a sufficient number of measurement points. In areas with sparse measurement points the interpolation method is also limited to only a rough representation of the real conditions.

Figure 6: Bed level changes after 6.5 years.

Figure 7: Annual bedload discharge. The estimation is based on [6]

The differences in the initial sediment condition cause significant differences in the results of the numerical simulations. That applies especially for bed level changes and to a lesser extent also for the bedload discharges. The resulting high sensitivity of the numerical model with regard to the initial sediment condition shows the importance of a conscientious generation of the initial sediment condition.

Another disadvantage of the pre-simulation is, that it intensifies the weaknesses of numerical model by embossing them into the initial sediment condition. Especially for a long term pre-simulation, as is used for this study, this becomes a serious problem. The simulation based on a spatially interpolated initial condition has overestimated the initial erosion clearly, probably due to initial effects. Therefore it seems reasonable to use a combination of both methods. First, an initial sediment condition should be generated by a spatial interpolation, which is ideally as close as possible to the measured data. Second, a short pre-simulation should be conducted using the interpolated initial sediment condition. This approach could decrease the initial effects, without getting the disadvantages of a long pre-simulation. Therefore it seems worth to test such a combined approach in a further reaching study. The effort of such a combined method, in terms of computation time, would be more than a pure interpolation, but still less than a long pre-simulation.

In addition, a more sophisticated interpolation algorithm could be applied e.g. Kriging [7] to improve spatial interpolation itself.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study results from the author's master thesis, which was supported by the Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute. The author's particular thanks go to his thesis supervisors for their support and advice.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Bleyel, R. Kopmann, „Influence of the layer model on a 2D sediment transport model: Hirano-Ribberink versus C-VSM“, Proc.

of the 25th TELEMAC-MASCARET User Conference 2018, <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11970/105196>

- [2] L. Backhaus, T. Brudy-Zippelius and T. Wenka, “Comparison of morphological predictions in the Lower Rhine River by means of a 2-D and 3-D model and in situ measurements”, Proc. River Flow 2014, International Conference on Fluvial Hydraulics, Lausanne
- [3] M. Utz, “Einfluss der sedimentologischen Anfangsbedingung auf die numerische Modellierung des Feststofftransports” master thesis, 2018
- [4] TELEMAC-2D v7.0 User's Manual, 2014
- [5] SISYPHE v6.3 User's Manual, 2014
- [6] WSA Duisburg-Rhein, “Statusbericht Niederrhein – Erfolgskontrolle des Geschiebemanagements am Rheinstrom” Heft 1, 2008
- [7] J. P. Chiles, P. Delfiner: Geostatistics: Modeling Spatial Uncertainty. Wiley, New York 1999, ISBN 0-471-08315-1.

